

Physicochemical Parameters of Bottled Water Available in Umuahia Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The major aim of this study was to assess the physical and chemical composition of bottled water sold and consumed in Umuahia municipal area. Samples of brands of bottled water sold in Umuahia metropolis were analysed for their physical and chemical parameters. Values obtained for temperature was highest in brand B (30 degrees celsius) and a lower value was obtained in brand C (29 degrees Celsius). Dissolved oxygen was highest in brand C (975.50 mg/l) and lowest in brand E (128.20 mg/l). Colour value was 0.003 for brand B and lowest in brand C with a value of 0.011. Turbidity for brand D was (0.06 at 700mm), while biochemical oxygen demand for brand D was 160.20mg/l. Chemica oxygen demand (COD) was highest in brand E with a vakue of 255.30mg/l as compared to brand D which had the lowest value of 123.38mg/l. Potassium was highest in brand D (1.05mg/l) and lowest in brand B (0.60mg/l). Calcium was highest in brand A (40.10mg/l) and magnesium was highest in brand B. When comparing results to WHO standards, the samples were in conformity and fell within recommended range for safe consumption. However the relative levels of chlorine and phosphate found presuppose that most of the water brands studied had some water treatments. The results obtained from the present investigation might be useful in the future for monitoring the inflow of bottled water around Umuahia metropolis.

Keywords: Physico-chemical, Parameters, Bottled Water, Umuahia, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Bottled water may be defined as water that is intended for human consumption and that is sealed in bottles or other containers; which has no added ingredients except that it may optionally contain safe and suitable antimicrobial agents. According to the International Bottled Water Association, “Bottled water is a great

beverage choice for hydration and refreshment because of its consistent safety, quality, good taste and convenience”. Bottled water can be categorized into Artesian well water, distilled water, mineral water, purified water, sparkling water, well water, and so on according to their sources and state of purification. The mass production and marketing of bottled water witnessed an explosion in the late 20th century. In the global scenario, sales and consumption of bottled water have skyrocketed in recent years. From 1988 to 2002, the sales of bottled water globally have more than quadrupled to over 131 million cubic meters annually ^[1]. Bottled water sales worldwide are increasing at a rate of 10% annually^[1]. One of the main reasons for this trend is the compromised water quality provided by municipalities. Another reason may be the public perception that bottled water is essentially of high quality. The public perception and probably the reality is that bottled water is regularly of high quality ^[2]. This belief is encouraged by publicly reported problem of municipal tap water as well as the public perception of purity driven by advertisements and packaging labels featuring pristine glaciers and crystal clear mountain springs. However, many studies have shown that these beliefs need not always be correct. A four-year study conducted by the National Resources Defense Council (NRDC, 1999) revealed that about one-third of samples contained significant contamination, including synthetic chemicals, bacteria and arsenic, in at least one sample, out of more than 1000 samples of 103 bottled water brands tested. It also concluded that “an estimated 25% or more of the bottled water is really just tap water in bottle-sometimes further treated, sometimes not”. Even with limited independent testing done for bottled water, problems are periodically discovered. Many individual researches and studies in developed countries have shown that only because water comes out of a bottle doesn’t mean that it is definitely purer and safer than the tap water. Similarly, in the words of NRDC, “While much tap water is indeed risky, having compared the available data, we conclude that there is no assurance that bottled water is any safer”.

People buy bottled water for a variety of reasons, including fear of contamination, convenience, fashion, and taste or on the assumption that they are pure and fit for human consumption. As a result, global market for bottled water has witnessed tremendous growth in recent years as rising health awareness and increased need for convenience products have combined to drive sales.

Nigeria ranks third on the list of countries with inadequate water supply and sanitation coverage globally ^[3]. Water and sanitation in Nigerian is characterized by low levels of access to an improved water source (USAID, 2012; WHO, 2012; UNICEF, 2012). This situation has opened up a whole world of drinking water business in Nigeria by private investors and has led to the production of many brands of bottled and sachet (‘pure’) water in virtually every nook and cranny of the country available on sale. Yet, little if anything is known to the consuming public about the physical, chemical, microbiological and biological parameters of the water they buy and consume.

In Umuahia, the capital city of Abia State, several brands of bottled water are available on sale^[4,5,6] have investigated ground water quality available from several boreholes consumed within Umuahia metropolis. Hardly have any studies been carried out on the quality of bottled water available and consumed in this area. Hence, the present study sets out to investigate the physicochemical and bacteriological parameters of bottled water available in Umuahia Municipality.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the physico-chemical and bacteriological parameters of bottle water available in Umuahia. The specific purposes of this study are:

1. To analyse for the physicochemical properties of bottle water available in Umuahia Metropolis.
2. To identified any bacteriological composition in the bottle water available in Umuahia Metropolis.
3. To compare results with prescribed standards

Justification for the Study

In the wake of perennial inadequacy of drinking water in Nigeria, bottled water industry in booming in the country. Many brands of bottled water are now produced which are readily available in virtually everywhere in Nigeria especially in the urban centers. Well-to-do Nigerians prefer to consume water in this form because of the assumption that it is pure and fit for human consumption. Yet little if any studies have been conducted into the physical, chemical, microbiological and biological parameters of bottled water available especially in the study area. In view of beliefs that product standards are not stringent in the country, which may also affects bottled water quality and safety, bottled water available for human consumption in this study area may not always be as safe as presumed. Hence an attempt at assessing bottled water quality makes sense.

Further, safe drinking water is a fundamental right of humans. However, morbidity and mortality statistics suggest that water-borne diseases account for over 80% of health problems; especially in the developing lands of Asia, Africa and Latin America. Driven by the perception of purity, people switch to buying bottled water. The question still remains as to how pure the bottled water really is. People have the right to know the quality of water that they perceive to be pure. Hence, this case study is justifiable.

Water Quality

Water is an essentials element in the maintenance of all life forms, and most living organism cannot survive without it^[7,8]. In addition to being in abundant supply, the available water must have specific characteristics, signifying its quality^[9,10,11]. Traditionally, the most important of the quality characteristics has been the concentration of dissolved salt because of the relationship between salt and land productivity. Later, health related characteristics such as

presence of disease-causing microorganism became of importance. More recently, the introduction of anthropogenic chemicals that have impact on health when present in trace amounts has become a problem. Of all the water sources on earth, only 3% are good (in terms of quality or freshness). This include: surface water (rivers, lakes, streams and reservoirs) and groundwater. With the decline in the used of surface water for drinking water supply due to contamination, there is an increase in the reliance of ground water as drinking water source. Unfortunately, little attention is being paid to drinking water quality issues and quantity remains the priority focus during water supply projects. The need to define the quality of water has developed with the increasing demand for water which is suitable for specific uses and conforms to desired quality. Although water quality and water quantity are inextricably linked, water quality deserves special attention because of its implications for public health and quality of life . Truly, the danger that unsafe drinking water poses to health is enormous. Unsatisfactory, water supplies and unwholesome sanitary conditions can result in poor human health. A recent studied in Lagos, South Western Nigeria, on well and tap waters used as drinking sources revealed that all the well waters from the locations under study were contaminated

Worldwide, roughly 1.1 billion people lack access to safe water and 1.1 7 million people are said to die every year from water-borne diarrheal disease (Wikipedia). Consequently, the most fundamental need is for water that is suitable for drinking, food preparation and personal hygiene, that poses no risk is any way, to human health. Understandably, most stringent control of water contaminants and higher quality standard apply to water intended for human consumption than for other uses. These standards are expressed in terms of the microbiological, chemical and physical characteristics of water.

Although water is vital for life, it also serves as the commonest route of transmission of a number of infectious diseases. Thus, water quality must be ensured before drinking and the water we drink must be safe. Water quality refers to the condition of the water, including chemical, physical, and bacteriological characteristics, usually with respect to its suitability for a particular purpose such as drinking or swimming. With respect to drinking water, water quality is determined by its physical, chemical and microbiological properties. Globally, this serves as the standard parameter for assessment of water quality although wide variability exists in the range for establishment of standards in various societies and settings.

Safe drinking water is defined as water with microbial, chemical and physical characteristics that meet WHO guidelines of national standards on drinking water quality. This is reflected by various physical, chemical and biological conditions which in turn are influenced by natural and anthropogenic sources. Water quality parameters like alkalinity, hardness, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), chloride, Total Dissolved Solid (TDS), and so on add to the aesthetic value of water, while parameters like ammonia, lead, arsenic and nitrate may cause adverse health effects. Appropriate amount of chloride content and hardness are desirable but higher content of the same makes the water unaesthetic. Similarly higher content of phosphate, nitrate, ammonia, iron, are undesirable. Some other chemical constituents like arsenic, lead, and other heavy metals may be toxic.

From microbiological point of view, drinking water should be free from any kinds of pathogens as well as opportunistic micro flora. Although there are a number of micro-organisms present in water that may pose health threat like *Salmonella* spp, *Shigella* spp, Coliforms, *Mycobacterium* spp etc., coliforms are used to assess water quality. Coliforms are gram negative rod shaped bacteria capable of growth in presence of bile salts and able to ferment lactose at 35-37°C with the production of acid, gas and aldehyde within 24 – 48 hours. They are oxidizing negative and non-spore forming. Coliform organisms (*E.coli*) have long been recognized as a suitable microbial indicator of drinking water quality largely because it is easy to isolate and enumerate them. They are present in the intestine of warm blooded animals including humans. Thus, their presence in water samples indicates the presence of fecal matter and the possible presence of pathogenic organisms of human origin.

If other pathogenic microbes are used as an indicator, then there is high chance of getting contaminated and the sample taken should be large to trap pathogens, since their numbers decrease as they mix with water (Budhathoki, 2010). The micro-organisms in water are capable of causing various diseases like typhoid, cholera, diarrhea, dysentery, hepatitis etc. According to WHO, unsafe water supply is a major problem and fecal contamination of water sources and treated water is a persistent problem worldwide. Globally, 1.1 billion people rely on unsafe drinking water sources from lakes, rivers and open wells. The majority of these are in Asia (20%) and Sub-Saharan Africa (42%). The use of these unsanitary sources helps to explain why 90% of human infections in less developed countries are caused by water borne diseases (Pimentel et al., 2004). The WHO has estimated that up to 80% of all sickness and disease in the world is caused by inadequate sanitation, pollution or unavailability of water. Hence it is necessary to purify and disinfect water before it is available for drinking. Many researches and studies have revealed that tap water do not ensure the quality of water. According to the National Water Quality Association, 56% of all people are worried about the quality of municipally treated tap water. With the rising concern on public health, people choose bottled water over tap water.

Bottled Water

Since the commencement of human history, people have explored various possibilities to convey fresh water from its source to their locale. During the height of the Roman Empire, aqueducts were erected to distribute water to the cities, and containers made from clay, materials of natural fibers and animal pelts were utilized to carry water in less significant amounts. In time, due to war, and then roaming lengthy distances by automated vehicles and sports activities such as hiking predisposed the inevitability for people to devise better ways for moving portable water.

Common Assumptions Surrounding Bottled Water

The bottled water industry is one of the fastest growing beverage industries in the world with millions of people preferring to consume water in this form as the healthy option of choice because of the following assumptions:

1. Bottled water is exponentially more expensive than tap water

Whilst some bottled water companies sell their products at fairly high prices, there are others whose products retail at very affordable prices. When you actually consider the quality of bottled water, the time and intensity of the purification process, and the associated health benefits, you will find - like so many others - that it is not expensive at all when considering the advantages.

2. The regulations relating to bottled water safety are not as stringent as the ones regulating tap water.

This is quite far from the truth. All water that is sold to the public for consumption is regulated and tested thoroughly before it ever reaches your lips - be it from the tap or from a bottle. While South Africa's drinking water is considered excellent, our bottled water companies package and sell safe and healthy products to the public. The bottled water standards here are also of international acclaim.

3. Bottled water companies are draining the world's water supplies

This statement is simply ridiculous. For instance, in a study carried out by the Drinking Water Research Foundation, bottled water accounts for around 0.02% of the total groundwater extracted from the USA annually. This figure is made to look even more minuscule when you compare it to the 68% of total groundwater used by the agriculture industry and the 20% used as public drinking water annually.

4. All bottles used by bottled water companies have to be rigorously tested to ensure they are free from any contaminants or undesirable substances. A lot of work goes into making sure that the bottles as well as their contents are safe for human consumption. Many of the myths surrounding bottled water may, at best be seen as hypotheses that need to be tested to ascertain their authenticity.

Benefits of Bottled Water

Bottled water is popular, though it's not always looked on with favour. Some people refer to it as an unneeded expense, and others bemoan the additional waste in the city landfill. However, it is an easy, convenient way to get needed fluids. There are several benefits of having and drinking bottled water.

1. Travelling: Bottled water is easy to drink while driving down the road. It hydrates much better than coffee or fizzy drinks, and as it has a lid, it's less likely to spill. Even if it does, it won't stain most clothing.

2. **Emergency Preparedness:** One of the biggest problems after a disaster is a lack of clean drinking water. Damage to sewers and water mains can mix the nasty stuff and leave you without either. Keeping a supply on hand can relieve at least one worry after something has happened.
3. **Convenience:** There are no dirty dishes to wash, and having it next to your computer instead of coffee can prevent sticky spills into the keyboard
4. **Proper Hydration:** Most people are dehydrated. We don't drink enough water, and the fluids we do use tend to be caffeinated. That doesn't help, as caffeine acts like a diuretic, making the problem worse. I've tried an experiment, and here are the results. If a liquid is sitting next to where I'm working, I will unconsciously drink it. It doesn't matter what it is. It's amazing how fast it disappears and I don't even know I'm drinking it.
5. **Weight Loss:** Many beverages have considerable calories, water has none. It also has no caffeine, which may cause water weight gain. Rather, it flushes out toxins than adding more, which can also help in weight loss.

Parameters of Bottled Water

Physical parameters

Physical characteristics of water (temperature, colour, taste, odour and others.) are determined by senses of touch, sight, smell and taste. For example temperature by touch, colour, floating debris, turbidity and suspended solids by sight, and taste and odour by smell .

Temperature

The temperature of water affects some of the important physical properties and characteristics of water: thermal capacity, density, specific weight, viscosity, surface tension, specific conductivity, salinity and solubility of dissolved gases. Chemical and biological reaction rates increase with increasing temperature. Reaction rates usually assumed to double for an increase in temperature of 10 °C. The temperature of water in streams and rivers throughout the world varies from 0 to 35 °C.

Colour

Colour in water is primarily a concern of water quality for aesthetic reason. Coloured water give the appearance of being unfit to drink, even though the water may be perfectly safe for public use. On the other hand, colour can indicate the presence of organic substances, such as algae or humic compounds. More recently, colour has been used as a quantitative assessment of the presence of potentially hazardous or toxic organic materials in water.

Taste and Odour

Taste and odour are human perceptions of water quality. Human perception of taste includes sour (hydrochloric acid), salty (sodium chloride), sweet (sucrose) and bitter (caffeine). Relatively simple compounds produce sour and salty tastes. However sweet and bitter tastes are produced by more complex organic compounds. Human detect many more tips of odour than tastes. Organic materials discharged directly to water, such as falling leaves, runoff, etc., are sources of tastes and odour-producing compounds released during biodegradation.

Turbidity

Turbidity is a measure of the light-transmitting properties of water and is comprised of suspended and colloidal material. It is important for health and aesthetic reasons.

Solids

The total solids content of water is defined as the residue remaining after evaporation of the water and drying the residue to a constant weight at 103 °C to 105 °C. The organic fraction (or volatile solids content) is considered to be related to the loss of weight of the residue remaining after evaporation of the water and after ignition of the residue at a temperature of 500 °C. The volatile solids will oxidize at this temperature and will be driven off as gas. The inorganic (or fixed solids) remind as inert ash. Solids are classified as settle able solids, suspended solids and filterable solids. Settle able solids (silt and heavy organic solids) are the one that settle under the influence of gravity. Suspended solids and filterable solids are classified based on particle size and the retention of suspended solids on standard glass-fibre filters.

Chemically, water is a compound of hydrogen and oxygen, having the formula H₂O. It is chemically active, reacting with certain metals and metal oxides to form bases, and with certain oxides of nonmetals to form acids. It reacts with certain organic compounds to form a variety of products, e.g., alcohols from alkenes. Because water is a polar compound, it is a good solvent. Although completely pure water is a poor conductor of electricity, it is a much better conductor than most other pure liquids because of its self-ionization, i.e., the ability of two water molecules to react to form a hydroxide ion, OH⁻, and a hydronium ion, H₃O⁺. Its polarity and ionization are both due to the high dielectric constant of water.

Water has interesting thermal properties. When heated from 0°C, its melting point, to 4°C, it contracts and becomes more dense; most other substances expand and become less dense when heated. Conversely, when water is cooled in this temperature range, it expands. It expands greatly as it freezes; as a consequence, ice is less dense than water and floats on it. Because of hydrogen bonding between water molecules, the latent heats of fusion and of evaporation and the heat capacity of water are all unusually high. For these reasons, water serves both as a heat-transfer medium

(e.g., ice for cooling and steam for heating) and as a temperature regulator (the water in lakes and oceans helps regulate the climate).

The chemical characteristics of natural water are a reflection of the soils and rocks with which the water has been in contact. In addition, agricultural and urban runoff and municipal and industrial treated wastewater impact the water quality. Microbial and chemical transformations also affect the chemical characteristics of water

Inorganic Minerals

Runoff causes erosion and weathering of geological formation, rocks and soils as the runoff travels to the surface-water bodies. During this period of contact with rocks and soils the water dissolves inorganic minerals, which enter the natural waters. Inorganic compounds may dissociate to varying degrees, to cations and anions.

Major Cations

Major cations found in natural water include calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), sodium (Na^+) and potassium (K^+). Calcium (Ca^{2+}), is the most prevalent cation in water and second inorganic ion to bicarbonate in most surface water.

The principal concern about calcium is related to the fact that calcium is the primary constituent of water hardness. Calcium precipitates as CaCO_3 in iron and steel pipes. A thin layer of CaCO_3 can help inhibit corrosion of the metal. However, excessive accumulation of CaCO_3 in boilers, hot water heaters, heat exchangers, and associated piping affects heat transfer and could lead to plugging of the piping. Calcium concentration of up to 300 mg/L or higher have been reported. However, calcium concentrations of 40 to 120 mg/L are more common.

Magnesium is not abundant in rocks as calcium. Therefore, although magnesium salts are more soluble than calcium, less magnesium is found in surface water. Sodium and potassium are commonly found as free ions. The concentration of these cations in natural water usually are low. Other constituents in natural water in concentration of 1 mg/L or higher include aluminum, boron, iron, manganese, phosphorus and etc.

Major Anions

Major anions include chloride, sulfate, carbonate, bicarbonate, fluoride and nitrate. Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) is the principal anion found in natural water. These ions are very important in the carbonate system, which provides a buffer capacity to natural water and is responsible in a great measure for the alkalinity of water.

One source of bicarbonate ions (HCO_3^-) in natural water is the dissociation of carbonic acid (H_2CO_3) that is formed when carbon dioxide (CO_2) from the atmosphere, or from animal (e.g. fish) and bacterial respiration, dissolves in water.

In addition to bicarbonates (HCO_3^-) anions such as chlorides (Cl^-), sulfates (SO_4^{2-}), and nitrates (NO_3^-) are commonly found in natural water. These anions are released during the dissolution and dissociation of common salt deposits in geologic formations.

The concentration of the chlorides anions (Cl^-) determines the water quality because the quality of water get worse after increasing in the concentration of this anions which limit possibilities of using of natural water for different purposes (household, agriculture, industry and etc.). Principal source of the chlorides anions (Cl^-) in natural water are magmatic rock formations that include chlorine-content minerals. The second source of this anions is Ward Ocean from where a considerably amount of chlorides anions (Cl^-) enter in the atmosphere. From atmosphere chlorides anions (Cl^-) enter in the natural water in result of interaction between precipitation and soil.

The sulfates anions (SO_4^{2-}) are frequently found in natural water as the result of the chemical dissolution. Sulfates anions (SO_4^{2-}) enter in natural water as the result of the oxidation of the substances from plant and animal origin. The increase concentration of the sulfates anions (SO_4^{2-}), at one hand brings about change for the worse of some physical characteristics of water (taste, smell and etc.) and on the other hand has destructive influence upon human consumption. The concentration of the sulfates anions (SO_4^{2-}) fluctuates in a wide range in surface water - from 5 mg/l to 60 mg/l.

Nitrate anions (NO_3^-) are found in natural water as the result of the bacteriological oxidation of nitrogenous materials in soil. That is why the concentration of these anions rapidly increases in summer when the process of the nitrification takes place very intensively. Another important source for dressing of the surface water with Nitrate anions (NO_3^-) are precipitations, which absorb nitric oxides and convert them into nitric acid. A great deal of nitrate anions (NO_3^-) enters in surface water together with domestic water and water from industry, agriculture and etc. Nitrate anions (NO_3^-) are one of the indicators for the degree of the pollution with organic nitrate-content substances.

pH and Alkalinity of Water

Alkalinity is defined as the capacity of natural water to neutralize acid added to it. Total alkalinity is the amount of acid required to reach a specific pH (pH = 4,3 to 4,8).

Acidity

Acidity is the "quantitative capacity of aqueous media to react with hydroxyl ions". Titration with a strong base (NaOH) to define end points (pH = 4,3 and pH = 8,3). Acidity indicates the corrosiveness of acidic water on steel, concrete and other materials.

Hardness

Hardness is correlated with TDS (Total dissolved solids). It represents total concentration of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions, and is reported in equivalent CaCO_3 . Other ions (Fe^{2+}) may also contribute. Hardness expressed as mg/L CaCO_3 is used to classify waters from "soft" to "very hard".

Total Dissolved Solids

Total dissolved solids (TDS) is a measure of salt dissolved in a water sample after removal of suspended solids. TDS is residue remaining after evaporation of the water. The TDS load carried in streams throughout the world has been estimated by Livingston (1963) to 120 mg/L .

Conductivity

The concentration of total dissolved solids (TDS) is related to electrical conductivity (EC; mhos/cm) or specific conductance. The conductivity measures the capacity of water to transmit electrical current. The conductivity is a relative term and the relationship between the TDS concentration and conductivity is unique to a given water sample and in a specific TDS concentration range. The conductivity increases as the concentration of TDS increases.

TDS and conductivity affect the water sample and the solubility of slightly soluble compounds and gases in water (e.g. CaCO_3 , and O_2). In general, the corrosiveness of the water increases as TDS and EC increase, assuming other variables are kept constant.

Organic Materials

Organic chemicals are made up of carbon (C), hydrogen (H), as well as nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O). Organic compounds are derived from living organism as well as industrial sources. A wide variety of assortments of organic compounds are produced in the chemical and petrochemical industries. Organic compounds also may contain sulfur (S), phosphorus (P), fluorine (F), chlorine (Cl), bromine (Br), and iodine (I).

Organic compounds in water also affect the water quality. Organic chemicals cause disagreeable tastes and odours in drinking water. Vinyl chloride, benzene and other organic contaminants are known carcinogenic agents, while chloroform is a cancer-suspect agent.

Natural Organic Matter

Organic materials are found in natural water as a result of a wide range of processes, together with precipitation and surface water, as the result of the interaction between soils and precipitation and etc. Organic materials in soils originate from plant and animal degradation products. These degradation products condense and polymerise into fulvic and humic acids to kerogen and finally coal. Chemical and microbial processes cause the transformation by first attacking functional groups and aliphatic side chains. Condensation and polymerization of various reactive groups result in larger, more aromatic molecules that decrease in solubility until kerogen or humin is produced. The end products are not soluble in acid or alkali and are resistant to biodegradation and chemical reaction.

Man-made Organics

Synthetic organic compounds include a broad variety of aliphatic and aromatic compounds. Many manufactured organic compounds may be found at very low concentrations in natural water. Isolation, identification and evaluation of health effects of these synthetic organics at low concentrations are lacking.

Dissolved Gases

The principal transfer of gas in natural water is the transfer of oxygen from the atmosphere to the water. However, gas transfer is also used to strip hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), ammonia (NH_3) and volatile organic compounds (VOC) from water. In both processes material is transferred from one bulk phase to another across a gas-liquid interface. For example, oxygen is transferred from the bulk gaseous phase (atmosphere) across the gas-liquid interface into bulk liquid phase (water). In the case of stripping volatile organic compounds (VOC) from liquid, the VOC is transferred from the bulk liquid phase (water) across the liquid-gas interface into the bulk gaseous phase (atmosphere).

Drinking Water Quality Assessment

Water is a compound of hydrogen and oxygen, having the formula H_2O . It is chemically active, reacting with certain metals and metal oxides to form bases, and with certain oxides of nonmetals to form acids. It is a very unstable substance which readily reacts with certain organic compounds to form a variety of products. Many substances dissolve in water and it is commonly referred to a universal solvent (The Columbia Electronic Encyclopedia, 2012).

Because of this, water in nature and in use is rarely pure and some properties may vary from those of the pure substance. Hence, the monitoring of the quality of drinking water available to the public makes sense.

The World Health Organisation has come up with guidelines for determining water safety and a strategy for ensuring safe water for the world populations 2013 - 2020. Many countries of the world have also developed local parameters for determining water quality within their setting taking after WHO's model. In Nigeria, the Standards Organisation of Nigeria in conjunction with the Federal Ministry of Health, Division of Water Safety has articulated the standards for ensuring quality drinking water from all range of sources – natural and man-made including packaged/bottled water.

Water Related Problems in Nigeria

Nigeria is a country with rich water resources. Yet, the country faces a number of problems regarding both its drinking water quality and availability. The municipal water supplies are inconsistent and unreliable. Not only the shortages in quantity, but also the compromised quality of municipal tap water has become a major public health issue. Throughout Nigeria, people are exposed to severe health threats resulting from water contamination by sewage, agriculture and industry. Owing to the impact of sewage, typhoid, dysentery, and cholera are endemic in Nigeria. These diseases account for high morbidity and mortality in Nigeria; especially among children.

Although being the dwellers of the capital city, we are neither in the state to proclaim proudly that the water we use is any purer nor can it be guaranteed that these kinds of epidemics can't occur in the valley. Thus, conveying message to the public about water quality and sanitation and at the same time, using disinfectants to purify water is a must in the present scenario. In the context of growing health consciousness and chronic water shortages, most of the urban residents have switched to bottled water as a safe alternative.

Water and Sanitation in Umuahia

Nigeria has obtained third position as one of the world's poorest countries in gaining access to water and sanitation. The WHO/UNICEF report for 2012 ranked Nigeria third behind China and India, as countries with the largest population without adequate water and sanitation. The challenge is critical as women and children trek long distances to fetch water from streams and ponds which are most times contaminated. The water sector was facing a lot of challenges but commended the contributions of development partners in the provision of safe drinking water, sanitation facilities and good hygiene practice to the nation's teeming populace. In Nigeria, access to improved water and sanitation poses a major challenge and water and sanitation coverage rates are amongst the lowest in the

world. Nigeria currently lags behind the MDG targets of 75% coverage for improved drinking water and 63% coverage for improved sanitation by the year 2015^[12].

In Umuahia, private investors sink bore holes and vend water direct from the ground to desperate consumers. Thus, the only source of water presumed to be pure and safe for human consumption in Umuahia is bottled water. As already expressed, the parameters of bottled water available in Umuahia has remained un-researched, hence the present study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

Umuahia is the capital city of Abia State in southeastern Nigeria. It is located along the rail road that lies between Port Harcourt to Umuahia's south and Enugu city to its north, and lies within latitude 5°32'N and longitude 07°29'E. Umuahia has a population of 359,230 according to the 2006 Nigerian census. The indigenous ethnic group is the Igbo. The major occupation of the people is trading and farming. Umuahia is indeed a railway town; well known as a railway produce collecting point for crops such as yams, cassava, corn (maize), taro, citrus fruits, cocoa and principally palm oil and kernels since 1916 (Wikipedia). Other economic activities include liquor brewing as well as palm-oil-processing. The National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI) and, of recent, the Michael Okpara University of Agriculture all at Umudike, is adjacent to the city. Annual rainfall ranges between 1900 mm and 2200 mm, almost evenly distributed throughout the wet season (April – October); while temperatures range between 25°C in January to slightly above 30°C in July. Relative Humidity is between 75% and 95% in January, but toward the end of the year, it reduces gradually as a result of the Hamattan (Metrological Service Centre, NRCRI).

Materials used for the study

Physicochemical parameters and microbial analysis carried out and Equipment used

S/No.	Parameter	Equipment / Method
1	Colour	Spectrophotometer
2	Turbidity	Spectrophotometer
3	Temperature	mercury Thermometer
4	BOD	Titrametric Method
5	DO	Titrametric Method
6	COD	Titrametric Method
7	Potassium (K)	Flamephotometer

8	Calcium (Ca)	EDTA Complexometric Titration
9	Mg	EDTA Complexometric Method
10	pH	pH meter
11	Conductivity (EC)	Conductivity meter
12	Total hardness	EDTA method
13	Chloride (Cl ⁻)	Titration method
14	Nitrate (NO ³)	Kjedhadly
15	Amonia (NH ⁴)	Kjedhadly
16	Phosphate (P)	Spectrophotometer
17	Sodium (Na)	Flame photometer

Adapted from Budhathoki, (2010)

Sample Collection

Five brands of bottled water of 1.5 litre capacity were collected randomly from various sales outlets in Umuahia with brand names labeled A, B, C, D & E. and taken to the laboratory for analysis of their physicochemical parameters.

Sampling Frequency

Water quality was analyzed twice for each brand of bottle water over a period of two months to capture differences in daily temperatures that may occur. The methodologies used to analyze various parameters are described below.

Analysis of Water Samples

Standard methods for physicochemical and microbial analysis of water and waste water (APHA, 1998) was used. Parameters such as pH, Electrical conductivity (EC), Total Hardness (TH), chloride (Cl⁻), Nitrate (NO₃^{-N}), Calcium (Ca), Nitrogen (NO₃), ammonium (NH₄^{-N}), Magnesium (Mg), Phosphate (P), Sodium (Na), Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Temperature, Colour and Turbidity were analysed. Obtained mean parameters of the brands were compared with WHO (2012) standards for drinking water.

Methods of Analysis of Water Samples

1. Temperature

For the determination of the temperature, water was collected in a beaker. Mercury filled Celsius thermometer was inserted into the beaker and reading was noted. The mean of the values of two frequencies for each sample was taken.

2. pH

pH was measured by automatic digital pH meter. The pH meter was first calibrated with a

standard buffer solution. The glass electrode was washed with distilled water. Then glass electrode was dipped in the beaker containing water sample until the reading stabilized at a certain point. Then pH reading was noted down.

3. Conductivity

The instrument used was digital conductivity meter. The conductivity meter was first calibrated with standard Potassium chloride solution of 0.01N. Then reading was noted.

4. Chloride

Chloride was measured by titration method. 50 mL of sample in a conical flask was taken. 2 mL of Potassium chromate was added to the sample solution. It was titrated against 0.02N silver nitrate until a persistent brick red color was appeared which the end point of the titration was. A blank by placing 50 mL of chloride free distilled sample water was also conducted.

Where, a = Volume of titrant (silver nitrate) for sample

b = Volume of titrant (silver nitrate) for blank

V = Volume of the sample in mL

N = normality of silver nitrate

5. Total hardness

Hardness is caused by the calcium and magnesium ions present in water. Total hardness was determined by EDTA method. This was done by titrating 100mL of sample in a conical flask and adding 1mL of buffer solution with Erichrome Black-T indicator against standard EDTA (Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid). The solution was changed from wine blue at the end point. Total hardness might be caused by the sum of all metallic cations other than alkali metals and expressed as equivalent calcium carbonate concentration.

Calcium hardness

Calcium hardness was determined by the same procedure as total hardness. Taking 50mL sample in a conical flask with 2mL of NaOH solution of 1N was titrated against EDTA solution using murexide indicator. At the end point, pink color changed to purple.

6. Magnesium hardness

Magnesium salts occur in significant concentration in natural waters which may be calculated as the difference between total hardness and calcium hardness. Magnesium hardness, mg/L (as CaCO₃) = Total hardness - Calcium hardness

7. Free CO₂

Free CO₂ in water can be determined by using titration method. For this 100 mL of sample was taken in a conical flask and 2 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added. Then it was titrated against 0.05N of NaOH from the burette until pink color was just appeared.

Calculation

Dissolved Oxygen

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) was measured by using APHA, (1998) method. The sample was collected in a 300 mL BOD bottle carefully, avoiding any kinds of bubbling and trapping of air bubbles in the bottle after placing the stopper. To the 50 mL sample taken in the conical flask 2 mL of manganese sulphate (MnSO₄) and 2 mL of Sodium azide solution was added well below the surface from the wall of the bottle. A precipitate was appeared. Then the stopper was placed tightly and the bottle was shaken by inverting the bottle repeatedly to insure proper mixing of the contents. The bottle was kept for some time to settle down the precipitate, 2 mL of conc.H₂SO₄ was added to it and shaken well to dissolve all the precipitate. Then 50 mL of sample were taken in a conical flask and titrate against sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) of 0.025N using starch as an indicator. At the end point the initial blue color changed to colorless.

Total Alkalinity

Total Alkalinity is the measure of the capacity of the water to neutralize a strong acid. The alkalinity in water is generally imparted by the salts of carbonates, bicarbonates, phosphates, nitrates, borates, silicates etc. together with hydroxyl ions in free state. Total alkalinity of water was determined by titrimetric method. 100mL sample in a conical flask with 2-3 drops of methyl orange was titrated against standard, 0.02N H₂SO₄. At the end point, yellow color was changed to pink color.

11. Phosphate

Phosphate (P) content in the given water sample was determined as inorganic phosphate by calorimetric method. In this method, 50mL of the filtrate clear sample was taken in a conical flask. 20 mL of ammonium molybdate was added to it. 5 drops of SnCl₂ solution was added to it. The solution becomes blue and the reading was taken at 690 nm on the spectrometer within 10-12 minutes. Same procedure was repeated for the standard solution of different concentration for distilled water. The concentration was determined with the help of standard curve obtained by plotting standard values against absorbance.

12 Nitrate-N

Nitrate content in the water sample was determined by Phenol disulphonic acid method. In this method, 50 mL of filtrate sample was taken in a por celain basin and was evaporated to dryness. It was cooled and

residue was dissolved in 2 mL of phenol disulphonic acid and dryness. It was cooled and residue was dissolved in 2 mL of phenol disulphonic acid and was diluted to 50 mL. 6 mL of liquor ammonia was added to develop yellow color. Then the reading was taken at 410 nm on spectrophotometer. Same procedure was repeated for the standard solution of different concentration and for distilled water. Then the concentration of Nitrate-N was determined from the standard curve obtained by plotting standard value against absorbance.

13 Ammonia-N

Ammonia content in a water sample was determined by colorimetric method. In this method 100 mL of water sample was taken in a volumetric flask. 1 mL of ZnSO₄.7H₂O was added, 1 mL of 10% NaOH was added into it. Then it was stirred and filtered. One drop of 50% EDTA was added and well mixed. Then 2 reagent (K₂HgI₄) was added. Then the reading was taken at 420 nm on spectrophotometer. The same procedure repeated for the standard solution of different concentration. Then the concentration determined with the help of standard curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Mean Values of Physical and Biochemical Parameters of some Table Water Brands available in Umuahia Metropolis

Table Water Brand	Colour EBC-Unit	Turbidity λ 700nm	Temp. °C	BOD Mg/l	DO Mg/l	COD Mg/l	K Mg/l	Ca Mg/l	Mg Mg/l
A (A-Nestle pure life)	0.010	0.004	29.80	178.90	156.10	217.71	0.80	40.10	7.29
B (Eva water)	0.003	0.002	30.00	188.40	167.50	142.54	0.60	20.04	17.02
C (Gossy water)	0.011	0.007	29.80	188.90	175.50	170.20	0.61	16.03	12.16
D (St. Nick water)	0.010	0.016	29.90	160.20	149.80	123.38	1.05	28.06	9.73
E (Udex water)	0.004	0.002	30.10	139.50	128.20	255.30	0.69	20.04	12.16
WHO MPL (2006)	15	5	25°C	5 - 100	5 - 50	5 - 100	>100	250	250

Key 1 (a): Explanation of Symbols

BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand, DO = Dissolved Oxygen, COD = Chemical Oxygen Demand, K = Potassium, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, WHO-World Health Organisation; MPL - Maximum Permissible Limit.

Key 2 (a): Explanation of Units of Measurement

EBC-Unit – Standard Reference Method (SRM) = (Abs 430 – Abs 700)

λ 700nm – Absorbance at 700 nm wavelength

$^{\circ}\text{C}$ – Degrees Celsius

Mg/l (Mg/l) - Milligrams / liter

Table 2: Mean Values of Chemical Parameters of some Table Water available in Umuahia Metropolis

BRAND	pH	EC μm	TH Mg/l	Cl ⁻ Mg/l	No ₃ ^{-N} Mg/l	NH ₄ ^{-N} Mg/l	P Mg/l	Na Mg/l
A (Nestle pure life)	6.94	0.14	65.05	152.44	2.80	8.40	18.62	2.10
B (Eva water)	6.80	0.28	60.05	138.26	4.20	7.00	27.34	3.50
C (Gossy water)	6.77	0.39	45.04	124.08	8.40	11.20	37.84	3.90
D (St. Nick water)	6.40	0.19	55.10	120.52	7.00	12.40	36.51	2.40
E (Udex water)	6.90	0.40	50.05	113.44	11.20	18.20	18.19	2.30
WHO MPL (2006)	6.5 - 9.2	100	100 - 200	>100	30	50	<100	100

Key 1 (b): Explanation of Symbols Continued

pH = Hydrogen ion concentration, EC = Electrical conductivity, TH = Total Hardness CL⁻ = chloride, No₃^{-N} = Nitrate, NO₃ = Nitrogen, NH₄^{-N} = ammonium, P = phosphate, Na = Sodium, WHO-World Health Organisation; MPL -Maximum Permissible Limit.

Key 2 (b): Explanation of Units of Measurement Continued

Ph - Hydrogen ion Concentration;

μm – Electrical conductivity

Mg/l - Milligrams / liter

DISCUSSION

Mean values of the physical and biochemical qualities of five brands of table water available and consumed in Umuahia Metropolis are shown in Table 1. The colour was calculated from values of absorbance measured at

430nm wavelength less than that obtained at 700nm wavelength and expressed as EBC – Units. The range of the colour values is 0.004 – 0.011 EBC-Units; while the turbidity had a range of 0.007 – 0.016 % absorbance. Turbidity is a measure of cloudiness of water which is caused by suspended solids and plankton that are suspended in the water column. Higher levels of turbidity in drinking water would pose several problems as that would mean ample availability of solids and planktons to fuel the food chain in the water^[13]. In drinking water, that would make for a high potential for chemical and biological interaction that can lead to deterioration and reducing of the shelf life of the drinking water. The level of the turbidity of the water brands was moderate, indicating a healthy and moderate amount of the solids and planktons in the samples and the potential for longer shelf life. The temperatures of the water brands ranged from 39.80°C to 30.10°C. The variations were not much among the table water brands. Temperature affects the concentration of dissolved oxygen in a water body. Oxygen is more easily dissolved in cold water. The biological oxygen demand (BOD) and the Dissolved Oxygen (DO) are some important aquatic parameters. The dissolved oxygen plays a crucial role in life processes of man and animals. In the present study the DO values found ranged from 128.20 to 175.50Mgl. Faster flowing clean water areas tend to be more oxygen rich because more oxygen enters the water from the atmosphere. In general low DO (> 3M/L) are stressful to most aquatic organism and water with low DO are considered hypoxic. The BOD of the water Brands ranged from 139.50 to 188 mg^l⁻¹. The Biological oxygen Demand is usually the amount of oxygen consumed by bacterial required for the oxidation of various chemicals in water.

The result of the chemical oxygen demand is also shown in table 1. This is a measure of oxygen equivalent of the organic matter content of the samples that is susceptible to oxidation by a strong chemical oxidant. The COD of the samples were 123.38 to 255.30mg^l⁻¹.

The chemical properties of the table water brands are shown in table 2. They include the pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), total Hardness (TH), chloride (Cl⁻), Nitrate – Nitrogen (NO₃^{-N}), Ammonia – Nitrogen (NH₄^{-N}), phosphorus (P), Sodium (Na), Potassium (K), Calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg). The pH of the samples ranged from 6.40 – 6.94. The water brands were weakly acidic to near neutral level and most acceptable pH for good drinking water is 6.50 – 7.0. The electrical conductivity is a measure of how well water can pass an electrical current which is usually a function of the inorganic dissolved solids content (the chemical elements). The conductivity ranged from 0.14 – 0.40

μS . High conductivity of EC can cause water balance problems for aquatic organism and decrease dissolved oxygen levels. (Sridhar et al., 2006). Hardness is frequently used as an assessment of the quality of water supplies. The hardness of a water is governed by the content of calcium and magnesium salts (temporary hardness, and largely combined with bicarbonates and carbonates with sulfates, chlorides and other anions. (Venkate-Sharaju et al., 2010). The levels of hardness in the water brands were $45.04 - 65.05\text{mg l}^{-1}$. Chloride content ranged from $113.44 - 152.44\text{mg l}^{-1}$; while $\text{NO}_3^{-\text{N}}$ and $\text{NH}_4^{-\text{N}}$ had a range of $2.80 - 11.20$ and $7.00 - 18.20\text{mg l}^{-1}$ respectively. Nitrogen occurs in natural waters as NO_3 and NH_4 . Ammonia is the least stable form of nitrogen and thus difficult to measure accurately. Nitrate is less stable and present in much lower amount than nitrate and Ammonia. These three compounds; $\text{NH}_4^{-\text{N}}$, $\text{NO}_3^{-\text{N}}$ and $\text{NO}_2^{-\text{N}}$ are interrelated. Through the process of nitrification, biological oxidation of ammonia to nitrate occurs. In this process, nitrite is produced as an intermediate product. The relative concentration of ammonia N in a given water sample is principally a function of pH, temperature and the electrical conductivity of the aqueous solution. Phosphorus is often the limiting nutrient for plant growth. It is one of the most important nutrients for maintaining aquatic fertility. It usually occurs in nature as phosphate. The results revealed that the concentration of PO_4 in the water brands ranged from 18.19mg l^{-1} to 37.84mg l^{-1} . The other basic cations assessed included Sodium, Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium. Table 2 revealed that their concentrations were 2.10mg l^{-1} to 3.90mg l^{-1} Na, 0.60mg l^{-1} to 1.05mg l^{-1} K, 16.03mg l^{-1} to 40.10mg l^{-1} Ca and 7.29mg l^{-1} to 17.02mg l^{-1} Mg. These cations are usually associated with the pH, electrical conductivity and temporary hardness in portable water. They also serve as natural buffers that can remove excess hydrogen ions that are usually responsible for high acidity level of water^[14].

Comparing the results with WHO standards (Maximum Permissible Limits), huge variance exists in virtually all the parameters tested, save in the case of Ph. In Colour, while WHO permissible EBC-Unit stands at 15, those for the samples ranged from $0.003 - 0.011$. In the case of turbidity, WHO permissible Absorbance at 700 nm wavelength is 5, $0.002 - 0.007$. While a temperature of 25°C is permissible by the WHO, all study samples overshoot this with values ranging from $29.90 - 30.10$. The local environment might go to explain this. Umuahia is located in the tropical rainforest climatic zone of Nigeria. Also, the season of the year during which the tests were run can further explain the high temperatures obtained.- having been conducted in April (Spring, whose temperatures are notably high in the study area). Atmospheric temperature is likely to affect that of bottled water in uncontrolled

environment. While the standard limits for BOD range from 5 – 100 Mg^l⁻¹, all the study samples overshoot this limit – range = 139.50 – 188.90 Mg^l⁻¹. In DO and COD parameters, the study samples overshoot the WHO's Maximum Permissible Limits of 5 – 50 Mg^l⁻¹ and 50 – 100 Mg^l⁻¹ respectively; ranges = 128.20 – 175.50 Mg^l⁻¹ and 123.38 – 255.30 Mg^l⁻¹ respectively. Potassium (K) content was sparse in all study samples relative to the WHO standard. While the WHO specifies >100 Mg^l⁻¹, those of the study samples ranged from as low as 0.60 – 1.05 Mg^l⁻¹. These, however were all compliant with prescribed standards. Calcium and Magnesium levels of the samples were also low and normal – ranging from 16.03 – 40.10 Mg^l⁻¹ and 7.29 – 17.02 Mg^l⁻¹, as against the prescribed 250 Mg^l⁻¹ in each case. The PH of the samples were all normal – varying from 6.40 – 6.94, conforming to the WHO standard of 6.5 – 9.2. Electrical conductivity (EC) and total hardness (TH) of the study samples were considerable low. While the WHO recommends 100 and 100 – 200 in each case, EC and TH ranged between 0.14 µm and 0.40 µm and 45.04 and 65.05 respectively. Chlorine (Cl⁻), Nitrite (NO₃^{-N}), Nitrate (NH₄^{-N}), Phosphorus (P) and Sodium (Na) contents of the samples were all found to be low – all falling below the WHO prescribed limits. The climatic setting of the study area and the season within which period was conducted are thought to account for the cases of disparities from the prescribed standards observed.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

All the physical, biochemical and chemical properties of the brands of water were found to be within the desirable limits, save for those as may have been influenced by the local environmental conditions of the study area – which represents the setting in which the brands are produced, marketed and consumed. However, the levels of chlorine and phosphate presuppose that most of the water brands studied had some water treatments. The results obtained from the present investigation shall be useful in the future in monitoring the inflow of water brands around the Umuahia metropolis.

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Appendix i

Brands of Bottled Water Available in Umuahia Metropolis

S/No.	BRAND NAME	PRODUCER	PLACE OF PRODUCTION	CLAIMED TYPE/SOURCE
1	Gossy	UAC Foods	Ikogosi, Ekiti State	Warm mineral water
2	Uzzi	Uzzi Water Co. Ltd	Mbano, Imo State	Natural spring
3	Eva	Coca Cola Bottling Co.	Lagos	Purified
4	Rich Vision	J. O. Akwuobi & sons	Umuahia	Purified
5	Nestle pure life	Nestle Nig. PLC	Lagos	Purified
6	St. Nick	Blessed Dika Motors	Umuahia	Purified
7	Aquafina	7 Up Bottling Co. PLC.	Lagos	Purified
8	Udex water	Dex Table Water Ltd	Umuahia	Purified
9	Sons Table Water	Sons Table Water Co.	Umuahia	Purified
10	Kechis Table Water	Ulover Int'l Resources Ltd.	Umuahia	Purified
11	MOWA Table Water	Dangote Group of Co's	Lagos	Purified
12	Master Energy Water	Master Water	Uturu	Purified
13	Mafo Table Water	Mafo Water Ltd.	Umuahia	Purified
14	Elixir Table Water	Ricker Hacker Enterprises	Aba	Purified
15	Cater Table Water	Cater Foods	Nnewi, Anambra State	Purified
16	Aqua Rapha	Aqua Rapha Int'l Ltd.	9 th Mile Corner Enugu State	Purified

17	La Voltic	Voltic Nig. Ltd.	Lagos	Purified
18	Genia	M. Genia Global Services Ltd.	Umuahia	Purified
19	C Way	C Way Nig. Drinking Water	Lagos	Purified
20	MOUAU Table Water	Michael Okpara Univ. of Agric. Umudike	Owerri	Purified

Source: Field Survey, 2022.